

USAID HESHIMU BAHARI

Policy Brief

Status of No-Take Fisheries Replenishment Zones (FRZs) in Tanzania

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Table of Contents

1.	3
2.	Error! Bookmark not defined.
3.	5
4.	7
5.	15
6.	19
7.	21

Context and Acknowledgements

This policy brief was prepared under the auspices of the USAID Heshimu Bahari Activity, 2022-27. The aim of the Activity is to strengthen marine protected area (MPA) and fisheries co-management area networks in Mainland Tanzania and Zanzibar, thereby enhancing marine biodiversity conservation, ecological resilience to climate change and coastal livelihoods and food security.

USAID Heshimu Bahari is implemented by Chemonics International, the Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS), and The Nature Conservancy (TNC) in close partnership with government partner institutions including the Ministry of Livestock & Fisheries (MLF) in Tanzania Mainland and the Ministry of Blue Economy & Fisheries (MoBEF) in Zanzibar, as well as a range of community, civil society and private sector stakeholders in coastal areas.

A particular focus of USAID Heshimu Bahari is to highlight the role that fisheries replenishment zones (FRZs) play in optimizing sustainable artisanal fisheries production, and to strengthen their effectiveness across the range of MPA governance regimes and contexts in Tanzania. This policy brief is a preliminary contribution to a collective effort on that topic.

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I. WHAT ARE FISHERIES REPLENISHMENT ZONES?

No-take fisheries replenishment zones (FRZs) are areas of ocean that are protected from all extractive and destructive activities, in particular fishing. FRZs are a globally recognized fisheries management tool designed to protect, nurture, and restore the productivity of fish stocks important for fishing, as well as marine biodiversity. In particular, FRZs protect habitats in which vital fish life-cycle processes such as spawning, recruitment, and juvenile development occur. In tropical seas, sub-tidal habitats supporting these processes commonly include coral reefs and seagrass beds. FRZs, also known as no-take zones, core zones, fisheries reserves, and fish sanctuaries, are a key feature of zoning plans for marine management and protected areas (MMAs and MPAs) across the Western Indian Ocean (WIO).

Critical to the value and functioning of no-take FRZs is the concept of *fish spillover*, whereby adult female fish, enabled to grow to a larger size through protection from fishing, produce exponentially higher numbers of eggs. These are exported to adjacent fishing grounds in the form of fish larvae and juveniles¹. That said, FRZs can only be effective if they are well designed in terms of objectives, size, location, connectivity, and effectively managed. A critical aspect of effective management is strong engagement of fishing communities, facilitating, and demonstrating understanding of the benefits of FRZs and obtaining informed consensus. Issues surrounding the ecological benefits and design of FRZs are outlined in section 3 below.

Fig 1: FRZs allow fish to grow larger and produce more offspring, thereby enhancing fisheries in adjacent areas².

To maximize the benefits of FRZs to fisheries production, the scientific community has proposed that FRZs should cover between 20 and 40 percent of marine habitats important for fisheries productivity³, with the weight of consensus settling around 35 percent. This, in part, provided the basis for a target 30 percent of all marine areas to be 'effectively conserved and managed' by 2030, adopted by parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) in 2022, to which Tanzania is a signatory.

¹ Halpern et al., 2010; Goni et al., 2011; Harrison et al. 2012; McClanahan, 2021

² Photo: Alfredo Barroso. Figure from Green et al. 2017. Fecundity calculations from Sadovy & Eklund, 1999 and Fonseca-Larios y Briones-Fourzan, 1998.

³ Botsford et al., 2003; Fogarty and Botsford, 2007

However, the 30 percent CBD target deals with a broader goal of effective sustainable management and leaves the percent coverage for full protection within marine areas undetermined. This is problematic in the context of FRZs where full protection is needed to achieve a fisheries replenishment function. Further policy work is therefore still needed in Tanzania to determine a target for protection of high-value fisheries habitats, especially coral reefs and seagrasses, that is both meaningful for fisheries replenishment and socially acceptable.

2. WHAT MAKES AN FRZ EFFECTIVE?

It has been demonstrated that adult and larval fish spillover from the boundaries of no-take FRZs to boost local fish stocks. In Kenya, for example, after Mombasa Marine National Park was fully protected in 1986, over the next decade catches near the park increased threefold compared with those farther away⁴. This strengthens the case that well-managed FRZs are a vital instrument for maximizing fisheries production.

Figure 2: A long-term FRZ study in Kenya demonstrated fisheries benefits⁵.

Fish biomass as an indicator of FRZ effectiveness. An initial question to address is how managers can know whether an FRZ is ‘working’. Studies show that fish biomass in particular is a reliable indicator of the ecological health of coral reefs and, by extension, of FRZs. The ecological threshold for sustainable fishing of reef communities is a fish biomass between 300 and 600 kg/ha. Reefs with fish biomass below 300 kg/ha show signs of ecological degradation, for example depleted fish communities lead to higher abundance of algae and sea urchins, which in turn cause coral reef degradation. By contrast, pristine reefs unaffected by fishing typically have fish biomass above 1,200 kg/ha⁶. Given this, it is helpful to pinpoint the critical variables that

⁴ McClanahan & Kaunda-Arara, 1996

⁵ McClanahan et al. 2021. Figure credit: WCS - Sarah Markes

⁶ McClanahan et al., 2011

affect fish biomass, to assist decision-makers in determining the design elements that contribute to an effective network of FRZs.

Design Factors. Designation of FRZs *per se* does not necessarily result in fisheries benefits. Several design factors must be considered including size, accessibility, and habitat cover and ecological connectivity, as outlined below. During implementation, management compliance (a compound of community acceptance and enforcement capacity) and duration of closure are significant variables.

- (i) *Size of FRZs* and management compliance were assessed in six Western Indian Ocean (WIO) countries by McClanahan et al., 2009. The study indicated that size impacts recovery rate and effectiveness, and estimated the minimum effective area of an FRZ at 5 km² or larger.
- (ii) *Accessibility/remoteness.* For understandable reasons, FRZs farther from towns have been found to perform better than those closer. Remoteness correlates significantly with higher fish abundance. McClanahan (2011) found that reefs located at nine or more hours travel time to the nearest regional town or market had a mean fish biomass of 2,450 kg/ha. This was three times higher than closures located nearer to towns, depending on the latter's size and age. Therefore, wherever possible, efforts should be made to locate FRZs in remote areas, although that also presents challenges in terms of regular surveillance and enforcement.
- (iii) *Ecological connectivity.* Linkages between coral reefs, mangrove habitats, and seagrass beds drive higher fish biomass and biodiversity. This is due to reef fish spending part of their juvenile stage in seagrass or mangrove habitats⁷. A study in the Caribbean indicated that reef systems with at least a 70km border with mangrove habitats had a more than threefold increase in fish biomass⁸. Fish biomass also depends on larval connectivity. Reefs that are net larval recipients (sinks) have double the fish biomass of source reefs that are upstream in terms of larval flow and are more resilient to human pressures⁹. Thus, location of FRZs should consider proximity to mangroves and larval flows of commercial fish species.
- (iv) *Duration of closure* of an FRZ. A study across the WIO¹⁰ projected how long it would take for a reef to recover to unfished biomass levels or to sustainable levels. The findings indicated that in Tanzania, where 45 percent of the sampled reefs had fish biomass below 300 kg/ha and 53 percent between 300 and 450 kg/ha, it would take three to five years to reach levels of fish biomass needed for sustainable fishing (450 kg/ha), six to seven years to reach levels of biomass that maximize biodiversity (600 kg/ha), and 14 to 17 years to reach levels of fish biomass of a mature unfished reef (1,150 kg/ha). These recovery durations, which assumed high compliance levels, highlight the need for a long-term commitment to increase areas under protection while at the same time finding ways to reduce the cost of long-term compliance.
- (v) *Community acceptance.* Probably the single greatest factor determining effective implementation of FRZs in the context of most WIO countries is community acceptance. If closure of a fishing ground does not have the support of community leaders and influential fishers it is very unlikely to be complied with. There are two self-evident reasons for this; one is the high importance of fishing to coastal community livelihoods, which means that closing areas to fishing has significant economic consequences at household and community level. This raises important social safeguard issues. The second is that

⁷ Mumby et al., 2004

⁸ Mumby, 2006

⁹ Fontoura et al., 2022

¹⁰ McClanahan et al., 2016

management authorities across all types of MPAs and co-management areas have limited resources for surveillance and enforcement, therefore compliance needs to be largely driven from within the community itself. For these reasons, successful FRZ implementation depends in most cases on: (i) a high level of community engagement and awareness-raising, and (ii) potentially mitigating the economic consequences of permanently closing fishing grounds, for example by sharing tourism revenues with a community in exchange for a reef closure. It is rare that an FRZ can be imposed successfully through assertion of top-down management authority alone.

3. POLICY & LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR FRZs IN TANZANIA

Table 1 below summarizes legal instruments relevant to establishment of FRZs in Tanzania. Table 3 in Section 4 below summarizes gaps in implementation of the governance framework for existing FRZs.

Table 1: Summary of legal instruments with provision for FRZ establishment

Legal instrument	Provisions
Marine Parks and Reserves Act, 1994 (Mainland)	<p>Section 8 provides for declaration of “any area within territorial waters or exclusive economic zone or any island or coastal area” as a marine park or marine reserve.</p> <p>Section 17 provides for preparation of zoning plans with description of zones and activities permitted within each zone.</p> <p>Section 23 (2) empowers the Minister to make regulations including regulating activities based on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the species of fish, animals, vegetation, or aquatic flora; (b) the methods employed in fishing, hunting, capturing and gathering of fish; (c) the type of nets, gear and other equipment permitted; (e) the geographical location in which activities may be conducted;
National Parks Act, CAP 282, 2002 (Mainland)	<p>Section 3 empowers the President, with the consent of Parliament, “to declare any area of land to be a national park”. In the case of Saadani National Park this has been taken to include a marine area.</p> <p>Section 23 provides that within a national park: “No person shall (without permit) hunt, capture, kill, wound or molest any animal (including fish) ...”</p>
Fisheries Act, 2003 (Mainland)	<p>Section 17 empowers the Minister to publish regulations for fisheries control measures including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (h) prohibiting fishing in designated areas;
District bylaws (Mainland)	<p>District bylaws have been used by several district councils to formalize designation of permanent fisheries no-take zones agreed by communities.</p>
Fisheries Act, 2010 (Zanzibar)	<p>Section 10 empowers the Minister “to declare any area in internal waters, territorial waters or Exclusive Economic Zone to be a controlled area in relation to all fish, fish products or aquatic flora ...”.</p> <p>Section 34 empowers the Minister to publish regulations including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (m) prohibiting or restricting the capturing, collection, killing or injuring of immature fish and provide for protection of spawning areas; (q) determining and imposing close periods;
Marine Conservation Act, (Proposed, 2023) (Zanzibar)	<p>Section 7 empowers the Minister to declare “any area within the coastal area or territorial waters to be a Marine Conservation Area” and further to declare “any part of a Marine Conservation Area to be a special area”.</p> <p>Section 15 provides that “A person shall not, within a special area for Conservation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) fish, hunt, kill or capture any fish or animal or disturb any egg, nest, roe, or spawn; (b) gather, collect, remove any aquatic flora or fauna, whether live or dead, or any sand, minerals, or aquatic substrates;

4. STATUS OF FRZs IN TANZANIA

4.1. Geographic distribution and size of FRZs in Mainland Tanzania and Zanzibar

There are currently 40 FRZs either established or formally proposed within nationally designated MPAs in Tanzanian marine waters. 25 are within marine parks, marine reserves or national parks in Mainland Tanzania, and 15 are within marine conservation areas (MCAs) in Zanzibar. Figure 3 below shows locations of the 40 FRZs and Annex I contains a full annotated list. At least 27 further FRZs have been proposed by communities under co-management initiatives within the past 10 years or so¹¹. 22 are in collaborative fisheries management areas (CFMAs) in Tanzania Mainland (in Mkinga, Pangani, Kibiti, Mafia and Kilwa districts), and five are in collaborative management group (CMG) areas in Zanzibar.

Figure 3: Locations of no-take FRZs within MPAs in Tanzania Mainland and Zanzibar

Of the 40 FRZs within national MPAs, area estimates are available for 27 of them¹², giving a total area of 113,340 ha. This is equivalent to 3.93 percent of Tanzania’s marine internal waters within which all the 40 FRZs are located. The Saadani National Park marine area is comprised of 87 percent of the designated 113,340 ha. The remaining 26 FRZs have a total area of 14,498 ha, with an average area of 558 ha. This is slightly above the size reckoned to be the minimum for fish biomass recovery¹³.

¹¹ Information from WWF, Mwambao, WCS and Sea Sense.

¹² For the remaining 13 FRZs in Zanzibar, boundary determination was still ongoing at the time of writing.

¹³ McClanahan et al., 2009

Figure 4 (right) presents the distribution of FRZ areas within marine parks and reserves in Tanzania Mainland. 17 of the 25 FRZs in Tanzania Mainland include significant terrestrial and intertidal areas within their boundaries, especially the 15 island marine reserves under MPRU. Thus, actual sub-tidal marine areas serving a fisheries replenishment function in those FRZs are smaller, significantly so in some cases.

This preliminary analysis highlights a need for more detailed mapping of existing FRZs in Tanzania Mainland, as well as for expediting operationalization of proposed FRZs in Zanzibar. For regional context, Table 2 below summarizes FRZ data in Tanzania and its two immediate Eastern African neighbors.

Fig 4: Areas of FRZ in Mainland parks & reserves

Table 2: Coverage of FRZs in Tanzania, Kenya and Mozambique¹⁴

	FRZs in national MPAs		FRZs in co-management areas	
	Number	Total area (ha)	Number	Total area (ha) **
Kenya	6	5,430 (4)	23	1,722 (17)
Tanzania	40	14,498 *	27	6,493 (18)
Mozambique	59	44,935	25	8,641 (25)

* does not include 98,842 ha for Saadani National Park marine area

** figures in brackets indicate number of FRZs for which the total area figure applies

4.2. Management effective of FRZs in Mainland Tanzania and Zanzibar

Consultations with on-the-ground stakeholders were undertaken during preparation of this policy brief to get a provisional indication of management effectiveness for each FRZ. Detailed anecdotal ratings are given in Annex I. Of the 40 FRZs in national MPAs in Tanzania:

- (i) **Only four are implemented effectively** to a high level, including Shungimbili Island Marine Reserve and Chamba cha Kati (MBREMP) in Mainland Tanzania, and Chumbe Island and Makangale/Tondooni in PECCA in Zanzibar.
- (ii) **A further 17 FRZs are reportedly partially effective** but still experience significant incursion by fishers; 14 in Mainland and three in Zanzibar.

¹⁴ Data from Rubens, 2023 and Rubens et al. (in prep.)

- (iii) **23 FRZs have no significant controls**, either because they are yet to be implemented (ten in progress in Zanzibar) or they currently have no significant controls on fishing (nine in Tanzania Mainland).

Only six of the 40 FRZs in national MPAs have physical boundary demarcation, four in Mainland and two in Zanzibar (see Annex I).

Complementing the anecdotal assessment above, Figure 5 below provides a more quantitative indication of the status of 17 of the 40 FRZs in national MPAs in Tanzania, presenting data on reef fish biomass from long-term regional reef monitoring by WCS. Key observations include:

- (i) *Higher fish biomass areas.* Only two FRZs have recent fish biomass levels above the estimated threshold typical of unfished WIO reefs, namely Maziwe Island in Tanzania Mainland and Mnemba Island in Zanzibar. Reportedly, neither of the two FRZs are entirely free from fishing, thus, this is likely an indication of their natural high ecological value as fish habitats. Other sites with relatively higher levels of fish biomass include Chumbe Island in Zanzibar and Makangale/Tondooni no-take-zone and Misali Island in PECCA.
- (ii) *Lower fish biomass areas.* Six FRZs, including three in Tanga (Ulenge Island Marine Reserve and two TACMP core zones), two in Dar es Salaam (Mbudya Island & Bongoyo Island Marine Reserves) and one in Zanzibar (Bawe Island) have levels of fish biomass that are even below the mean WIO level for unprotected, routinely fished sites. This likely reflects low or no control of fishing at those sites. For island marine reserves in Mainland, it might also reflect the fact that designation of some islands was not always primarily driven by ecological value for fish communities, rather it also provides a mechanism for broader management of uninhabited small islands, including developing their tourism potential.
- (iii) *Data gaps.* Recent fish biomass data (kg/ha) is only available for about one third of the 40 FRZs in national MPAs. Data is available for some other FRZs from other sources, for related parameters such fish abundance (no. of individuals per unit area), however it is not directly comparable. There is a need for a standardized metric in this context.

Figure 5: Fish biomass in 17 FRZs in Tanzania Mainland and Zanzibar¹⁵

Figure 5 outlines:

1. Data points represent fish biomass monitoring events within FRZs in national MPAs in Tanzania.
2. Colored polygons represent FRZs within which several monitoring events are located. Discrete monitoring events represent either different reef location within the FRZ or different year.
3. All data presented is from 2016 to 2023, except where indicated.
4. Monitoring events are arranged along the (horizontal) x-axis geographically, on a north to south gradient (left to right), first for Tanzania Mainland, then for Zanzibar.

Regarding management effectiveness in the 27 or so FRZs in co-management areas, 15 were established within the past five to six years and reportedly there are active efforts by shehia fishing committees (SFCs) or beach management units (BMUs)¹⁶ to implement them, with facilitation from NGO partners and local

¹⁵ All data from Tanzania Program, Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS).

¹⁶ Information from Mwambao, WCS and WWF Tanzania

authorities. The other 12 community FRZs are a legacy from earlier co-management initiatives, especially in Kibiti District and are likely not active.

Table 3: Gaps in implementation of governance framework for existing national FRZs

MMA Category	Gaps
Marine parks (Mainland)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The nine sub-tidal core zones in TACMP, MIMP and MBREMP marine parks are described in the respective General Management Plan (GMP)s but their boundaries are not formally designated in subsidiary regulations, as per Section 23 of the MPR Act of 1994. MPRU staff report that this does not currently impede them from prosecuting illegal fishing in core zones. 2. The current GMP for MBREMP from 2011 does not contain boundary descriptions or coordinates for MBREMP core zones, only a map.
Marine reserves (Mainland)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Boundary descriptions in several existing marine reserve gazettelement notices have coordinates that do not match the intended boundary. The boundaries need to be re-mapped. 4. Six marine reserves (Makatumba, Kendwa and Sinda Islands in Dar es Salaam and Nyororo, Shungimbili and Mbarakuni in Mafia Island), do not have GMPs. 5. The GMP for four other Dar es Salaam marine reserves from 2005 are overdue for review.
Marine Conservation Areas (MCA) (Zanzibar)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The Zanzibar Fisheries Act of 2010 does not contain an explicit provision for designation of FRZs, however that is expected to be rectified by the proposed Marine Conservation Act of 2023 currently under preparation. 7. With the exception of Chumbe Island, no FRZs in Zanzibar have yet been formally designated in subsidiary legal instruments.
Community co-management areas (Mainland and Zanzibar)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Most FRZ boundaries agreed with communities in Mainland have not yet been formalized in district bylaws. 9. For FRZs agreed with communities in Zanzibar which are not included in MCA GMPs, there is currently no legal instrument by which to formalize designation.

5. OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES FOR FRZs IN TANZANIA

Opportunities:

- (i) *Commitment by United Republic of Tanzania to increase marine areas under effective conservation and management* is manifest in Tanzania's endorsement of the 30 percent target set at COP 15 - Convention on Biodiversity in 2022 (Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework), as well as to SDG 14.5. Strengthening FRZ implementation within existing MPA networks would directly contribute to the CBD target, including community and private-sector-led FRZs that are often not accounted for in global MPA estimates and databases.

- (ii) ***Commitment by United Republic of Tanzania to blue economy development and national marine spatial planning (MSP).*** The United Republic of Tanzania has stated its commitment to sustainable blue economy development and to national MSP as an important tool towards that. The VPO-URT is in process of developing a comprehensive Blue Economy Policy and has recently published an MSP Scoping Study¹⁷. Establishing and strengthening a network of FRZs can both benefit from, and contribute to, anticipated marine spatial planning processes.
- (iii) ***Best-practice leadership in engaging in FRZ co-management arrangements.*** Currently, FRZs in Tanzania with a higher level of management effectiveness have mostly been co-developed and/or co-managed with private sector and civil society partners, including at Chumbe and Mnemba Islands, Makangale-Tondooni, Maziwe and Shungimbili Island. This already positions Tanzania as a best-practice leader on co-management of FRZs within the WIO and there are opportunities to expand the approach.
- (iv) ***Contribute to growth and sustainability of the marine tourism economy*** by protecting high value marine biodiversity assets within FRZs, adding value to tourism activities including snorkeling, scuba diving and underwater photography. Existing initiatives at Chumbe, Mnemba and Shungimbili Islands demonstrate the possibilities.

Challenges:

- (i) ***Limited management effectiveness in existing FRZs in Tanzania Mainland and Zanzibar.*** A high level of management effectiveness in FRZs is important because even a relatively small amount of fishing activity can significantly diminish the fisheries replenishment function of an FRZ, especially if larger-sized fish are removed. Currently, fishing activity is reportedly not effectively controlled in up to 90 percent of FRZs in national MPAs. Underlying this are challenges surrounding community acceptance and resources available for enforcement.
- (ii) ***Community acceptance of, and support for, FRZ implementation.*** Community acceptance of FRZs undoubtedly varies across Tanzania but findings in Section 3 indicate it is broadly weak. This represents a major challenge requiring a high level of ongoing engagement and awareness-raising with fishing communities, and also innovative approaches to benefit-sharing and mitigation of livelihood losses.
- (iii) ***Social safeguards.*** There is a parallel challenge of ensuring that social safeguards are fully respected in the context of FRZ network strengthening, including respecting customary access rights, equitable participation and livelihood security.
- (iv) ***Sustainable financing for FRZ enforcement within MPAs and co-management areas*** is a major challenge. Mainland MPAs and CFMAs in particular do not currently generate sufficient revenue to cover management costs. Innovative mechanisms for securing long-term sustainable financing for MMA management is urgently needed.
- (v) ***Legal & physical status of FRZs.*** There remain gaps in legal designation of FRZ boundaries within both national MPAs and co-management areas. Most are not yet physically demarcated. Six marine reserves in Mainland don't have management plans.

¹⁷ URT, 2023

Fig 6. Five of the six more effectively managed FRZs in Tanzania are co-managed with tourism private sector or civil society partners (CSOs)

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR STRENGTHENING FRZ IMPLEMENTATION IN TANZANIA

Based on the above findings, the following points are recommended for consideration by MPA management authorities and NGO, private sector and civil society partners:

(i) *FRZs are a critical tool for optimizing artisanal fisheries production*

In particular coral reef-associated demersal fish communities. In the context of long-term trends of increasing artisanal fishing effort, controlling illegal gears and designating FRZs are the two most viable means of controlling unsustainable overfishing.

(ii) *Design a network of optimally-located FRZs in Tanzanian nearshore waters*

The national commitment to marine spatial planning presents a timely opportunity for systematic design of a network of FRZs across nearshore waters in Mainland Tanzania and Zanzibar, with the primary aim of replenishing demersal fish stocks. Such design should be based on robust scientific data that can be generated expeditiously. Design should integrate existing FRZs and take into account documented best-practice on effective design, benthic ecological values, larval connectivity, fishing patterns and community acceptance. A strengthened FRZ network can be embedded into existing frameworks of government-run MPAs and community-led co-management areas.

(iii) *Develop site-specific strategies to create high-value demonstration FRZs*

There is an opportunity to focus on boosting the management effectiveness of selected existing high-value FRZs within national MPAs, with the aim of recovering their fish biomass to levels above 1000kg/ha within 3-4 years. Such FRZs can then potentially serve to demonstrate the benefits of FRZs to surrounding communities. Strategies could variously include:

- co-management partnerships with tourism private sector & CSOs
- engaging communities to secure wider consensus on the value of FRZs
- community communication campaigns on the fisheries benefits of FRZs
- innovative community compliance incentives including benefit-sharing
- physical boundary demarcation
- strengthening enforcement and applying innovative, low-cost surveillance technology

(iv) *Establish new FRZs guided by optimal network design & community acceptability*

MoBEF and MLF-MPRU and local authorities, with support of NGO, private sector and civil society partners strive to implement the FRZ network design generated from (i) above, subject to community acceptance and addressing social safeguards.

(v) *Strengthen information-base for FRZs*

There is a need to strengthen the information base for existing and proposed FRZs to enhance management, potentially including:

- MoBEF and MLF-MPRU to establish and host a web-based GIS platform for Tanzania's FRZ network to facilitate monitoring, evaluation and adaptive management of FRZs;
- filling existing gaps in FRZ boundary and habitat mapping including disaggregation of terrestrial island areas, intertidal areas and sub-tidal areas by habitat, and incorporate into the above FRZ GIS platform;

- establish and implement an ongoing, routine program of fish biomass assessment in all FRZs, involving all relevant co-management partners and research institutions to ensure that a common standardized methodology is applied across all FRZs, and that data is submitted and shared through the above-mentioned platform.

(vi) Legal designation of FRZ boundaries & general management planning

Respective MPA authorities in Mainland and Zanzibar to consider which gaps identified in Table 3 above require action.

(vii) Foster FRZ co-management partnerships.

Complementing (ii) and (iii) above, MoBEF, MLF-MPRU and district authorities to promote and nurture partnerships with tourism private sector and civil society entities in co-managing FRZs within MPA frameworks, building on the best-practice experience of initiatives such as those at Chumbe Island, Mnemba Island, Makangale-Tondooni no-take-zone, Maziwe Island and Shungimbili Island.

(viii) Foster best practice on community engagement & social safeguarding for FRZs

Complementing (ii) and (iii) above, MoBEF and MLF-MPRU and implementation partners to document best-practice guidelines on community engagement and social safeguarding for FRZ development, based on existing experience to-date in Tanzania Mainland and Zanzibar.

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ANNEX I: INVENTORY OF NO-TAKE FISHERIES REPLENISHMENT ZONES (FRZs) IN NATIONAL MPAs

Tanzania Mainland (listed north to south)

No.	MPA/ location	FRZ name	Legal status	Area (ha)	Effectiveness
1	Kirui Island MR	Kirui Island MR	GN 212, 2010	4,075	Demarcated
2	Mwewe Island MR	Mwewe Island MR	GN 212, 2010	49	No subtidal area
3	Kwale Island MR	Kwale Island MR	GN 212, 2010	1,255	Demarcated
4	Ulenge Island MR	Ulenge Island MR	GN 212, 2010	320	Demarcated
5	Tanga Coelacanth Marine Park	Shenguwe reef	GMP zoning plan, 2011	68	
6		Makome reef	GMP zoning plan, 2011	110	
7	Maziwe Island MR	Maziwe Island MR	GNs 137 & 150, 1975	1,705	
8	Saadani National Park	Saadani National Park	GN 188 of 2005	98,842	
9	Fungu Yasini	Fungu Yasini	GNs 137 & 150, 1975	943	
10	Mbudya Island	Mbudya Island	GNs 137 & 150 of 1975	1,120	
11	Pangavini Island	Pangavini Island	GNs 137 & 150 of 1975	172	
12	Bongoyo Island	Bongoyo Island	GNs 137 & 150 of 1975	674	
13	Makatumbembe Island MR	Makatumbembe Island MR	GN, 2006	641	
14	Kendwa Island MR	Kendwa Island MR	GN, 2006	149	
15	Sinda Islands MR	Sinda Island MR	GN, 2006	438	
16	Nyororo Island MR	Nyororo Island MR	GN, 2006	445	
17	Shungumbili Island MR	Shungumbili Island MR	GN, 2006	1,003	Demarcated
18	Mbarakuni Island MR	Mbarakuni Island MR	GN, 2006	1,494	
19	Mafia Island Marine Park	Outer Kinasi Pass	GMP zoning plan, 2011	615	
20		Kijiwenyara	GMP zoning plan, 2011	34	
21		Kitutia	GMP zoning plan, 2011	937	
22	Mnazi Bay & Ruvuma Estuary Marine Park	Ras Msangamkuu	GMP zoning plan, 2011	872	
23		Kisiwa Kidogo/Membelwa	GMP zoning plan, 2011	2384	
24		Chamba cha Kati	GMP zoning plan, 2011	149	
25		Kilindi reef flat	GMP zoning plan, 2011	441	

Zanzibar (listed north to south)

26	Pemba Channel Conservation Area (PECCA)	Makangale/Tondooni	Proposed in GMP, 2022	50	Demarcated
27		Njao Gap	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	
28		Fundu Gap	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	
29		Misali Island	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	
30		None	Hanga Reef	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD
31	Tumbatu MCA/ TUMCA	Mwana wa Mwana	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	
32	Mnemba Island Marine Conservation Area (MIMCA)	Muyuni North	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	
33		Mnemba Kaskazini	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	
34		Kichwani	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	
35		Pingwe Dongwe Lagoon	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	

37	Changuu-Bawe MCA (CHABAMCA)	Bawe Island East Reef	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	
38		Pange Sandbank & Reef	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	
36	Menai Bay MCA (MBCA)	Dongwe Mlango	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	
39		Chumbe Island Coral Park	Legal notice no. 99, 1994	55	Demarcated
40		Kwale Island	Proposed in GMP, 2022	TBD	

Note: FRZ effectiveness ratings in Column 5 are based on confidential consultations with on-the-ground stakeholders including relevant management agencies, NGOs and tourism private sector entities.